

Transdisciplinary Competencies for the Future: Bridging the Gap Between Emotional Intelligence, Digital Literacy, Inner Development Goals, and Employability

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ABSTRACT

Transformative potential of the knowledge economy of the XXI century, establishment of networked society, emergency digitization due to the pandemic and wartime measures have imposed elaborate interdisciplinary and interoperable demands on the marketability of Liberal Arts skills and competences, upon entering the workforce.

This study examines the gap between transdisciplinary future skills highlighted in the World Economic Forum's (WEF) "Future of Jobs" reports and those sought by learners in Coursera's Global Skills index. The emphasis lies on the role of Core skills combined with the Inner Development Goals (IDGs) framework in bridging these gaps. The proposed strategy roadmap links IDGs with the demands for future skills and Humanity-focused Higher Education (HiEd), besides, it provides actionable recommendations for HiEd staff, business schools and policymakers. By combining Inner Development with Leadership Skills and Digital Skills Programs in HiEd we may have a hope to stimulate employability for the AI age both for individuals' inner growth and collaboration/co-creation skills in teams and larger communities in a turbulent job market of 2025-2050.

The study results disclose the comprehensive review of dynamics of the digital skills development and application to construe interdisciplinary, AI-interoperable competencies of students and educators in Europe through the span of educational activities in the time-frame of the pandemic emergency digitization measures of 2020-2021 and wartime emergency digitization measures of 2022-2024 in Ukraine (including AI-enhanced communication as a staple of transdisciplinary education as of 2023).

The paper introduces a model of AI-interoperable digital skills for education and professional application in different social spheres. The survey analysis is used to evaluate the dimensions of interdisciplinarity, informed by the interoperability of soft skills, professional communication skills, and digital skills across contrasting frameworks of e-competence, Inner Development Goals, professional digital communication, and professional training.

Keywords: Inner Development Goals (IDGs), Interoperability, Transdisciplinarity, EQ, AI-literacy, Digital literacy, Digital skills, Employability, Higher Education

1. INTRODUCTION

Transformative shifts in the knowledge economy of the XXI century, Industry 4.0/5.0, Society 5.0 development and elaboration of networked society, emergency digitization due to wartime measures and the establishment of the AI Age have imposed pressing revisions onto interdisciplinary and cross-sectorial job market demands of Liberal Arts university graduates' skillsets, upon entering the workforce. This, in turn, stipulates reevaluation of the interdisciplinary approaches to comprehensive professional competences in education and application.

The pandemic induced amplified digitalization measures in the higher education sphere, informed by the need to take quick comprehensive action in order to achieve the overarching result to transform educational scenarios into interdisciplinary digital, blended, and hybrid frameworks. Taking into account the context of the erupted military intervention on Ukraine in February 2022, and the ensuing information warfare in various digital environments (social media, news coverage, digital communications), the specific value of the learning outcomes and outputs is allocated to the digitally enhanced educational communication as a tool of the internationally broadcast strife of Ukraine for freedom and sovereignty.

The rapid advancement of technology and evolving economic landscapes have reshaped the global job market, prompting organizations like the World Economic Forum (WEF) to analyze and project future skills demands through their "Future of Jobs" reports. Meanwhile, platforms such as Coursera's Global Skills Index provide a snapshot of the skills learners are actively pursuing today. Within this context, the Inner Development Goals (IDGs) framework has emerged as a key movement, aiming to cultivate the inner capacities necessary to meet the challenges of sustainable development and global complexity. As universities prepare students to navigate an increasingly dynamic

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and complex world, the integration of Emotional Intelligence (EQ) into curricula becomes vital. The future of education stands at the intersection of technology, sustainability, and human development. Here, smart campuses—equipped with AI, virtual reality (VR), and data analytics—are revolutionizing learning environments, offering tailored educational experiences that support emotional and cognitive growth [22]. Such technological advancements for more adaptive educational systems necessitate a shift in the role of educators from traditional knowledge providers to facilitators of essential competencies in both the digital age and sustainability [37].

The study **objective** is to introduce a comprehensive international perspective and data-corroborated research on multi-disciplinary, digital and AI literacies for pre/in-service teachers in Europe. That directs the inquiry to the aim of exploring the critical intersection of Emotional Intelligence (EQ), Inner Development Goals (IDGs), and future employability within higher business education frameworks. Specifically, the study aims to identify and analyze gaps between the future skills demanded by employers, highlighted in the World Economic Forum's "Future of Jobs" reports—and the skills prioritized by learners, as revealed by Coursera's Global Skills Index.

Through integrating the IDGs framework, this paper seeks to propose actionable strategies and recommendations for higher education institutions, educators, and policymakers. Ultimately, it advocates for embedding emotional intelligence and inner development within curricula to effectively bridge identified skills gaps, thereby preparing students holistically for the challenges of the digital and AI-driven era.

The **study design** includes the following steps:

- A systematic literature review and comparative content analysis with consistent transdisciplinary skills benchmarking, drawing explicitly on authoritative white papers published by the World Economic Forum (WEF), specifically the "Future of Jobs" reports from the years 2016, 2018, 2020, and 2023 [31], and Coursera's *Global Skills Reports* published annually from 2018 to 2023 [33];
- The modelling of interoperability between various competency principles, derivative of twenty-first-century skills [4; 7; 9] and projected digital and AI literacy requirements for education across core digital literacy frameworks (European e-Competence Framework [13], UNESCO revised ICT Competence framework for educators [29] and European Commission Digital Competence Framework: DigComp 2.2 [12]);
- The survey method application for diagnostic analysis of different digital literacy components and dimensions, as well as digital skills implementation, used to assess the parameters of efficiency of transforming real-life linguistic education practices into the digital and hybrid format;
- The identification of the interoperability between various groups of applied digital/AI skills and soft skills, instrumental to develop interdisciplinary professional competence.

The inquiry employs the combination of mixed methods [3, 8] – a proportional arrangement of quantitative and qualitative inquiry to assess in-depth aspects of subjective and individual quality estimation of digital distant, hybrid and AI-enhanced learning.

The survey structure comprised of 16 complex diagnostic questions (multiple choice, criteria comparison and Likert scale score types), divided into the *following categories*: 1) questions on overall assessment of digital and AI literacy level in the

framework of wartime emergency; 2) questions on diagnostics of specialists according to the established frameworks of digital/AI competencies and e-skills in the professional field; 3) questions on diagnostics of interoperability of linguistic / communicative / soft professional and digital skills.

The inquiry is conducted through the consistent study of digitization measures and outcomes for Arts and Sciences education programs in Ukraine, beginning with the timespan of the Covid-19 pandemic and transcending into the crisis paradigm of active warfare in different regions of Ukraine, across different education levels.

The inquiry's main findings disclose global event horizon and paradigm shifts [30] in the interdisciplinary trends of digital education in the pandemic timeframe and through the emergency of the warzone in Ukraine and in the EU; transformative changes of the network society and education as an interdisciplinary, multi-lingual socio-cultural institution in the digital age; experiences, challenges, digital advances and specific national gains in quality assurance of Humanities education in the sustainable and emergency paradigms.

The study results disclose the comprehensive review of dynamics of the digital skills development and application to construe interdisciplinary, AI-interoperable competencies of students and educators in Ukraine through the span of educational activities in the time-frame of the pandemic emergency digitization measures of 2020-2021 and wartime emergency digitization measures of 2022-2025 in Ukraine (including AI-enhanced communication as a staple of transdisciplinary education as of 2023).

2. FINDINGS

Conceptual Grid of the Inquiry

The following grid of groundwork concepts is applied to profile the digitization of higher education in the pandemic and wartime timeframes:

- TRANSDISCIPLINARITY;
- INTEROPERABILITY;
- DIGITAL LITERACY;
- COMPLEX SKILLS;
- AI-INTEROPERABLE DIGITAL SKILLS.

The meaning of TRANSDISCIPLINARITY is synthesized for the purpose of this study as an agglomeration of two or more fields of knowledge into one scope/goal of study, inquiry or activity [2; 6; 14; 17; 20].

The concept of INTEROPERABILITY is disclosed across different approaches [19; 26; 27] as a characteristic of an object, product or system, that allows its interface to be comprehensible, to work with other objects, products or systems.

A model of soft skills paradigms and digital AI-literacy frameworks INTEROPERABILITY in digital education is devised and corroborated through several iterations of surveys in the timespan of emergency digitization of 2022-2025:

- 1) European E-competence Framework Guideline (European Commission, 2021) [13], customized according to European Professional Competence Framework, accommodates the following soft skills in terms of digital competence requirements for vocational activity in FLE: service orientation; attention to detail, learning strategies, leadership and social influence, cognitive creativity and flexibility, coordination and time-management; human resources management;
- 2) UNESCO AI Competence Frameworks (teachers/students) (UNESCO, 2024) [29], customized for pre-service teachers of foreign languages, accommodates the following types of soft skills in terms of digital competence requirements:

collaboration, team-work, problem-solving, reasoning and ideation.

- 3) Digital Competence 2.2 framework (European Commission, 2023) [12] for general public, accommodates the following soft skills in terms of digital competence requirements for efficient digital citizenship: Communication and collaboration, creativity and adaptability, learning and innovation, trustworthiness, emotional intelligence, complex problem solving;
- 4) AI and Digital Transformation Competency Framework (UNESCO, 2024) [28] for public sector, accommodates the following soft skills in terms of digital competence requirements: service orientation; attention to detail, learning strategies, leadership and social influence, cognitive creativity and flexibility;
- 5) Skills in the Age of AI framework (WEF, 2024 [31] for workforce accommodates the following soft skills in terms of digital competence requirements: communication, critical thinking, creativity, emotional intelligence, adaptability, and decision-making;
- 6) Europe's Digital Decade policy program (Digital Decade 2030) [11] for countries accommodates the following soft skills in terms of digital competence requirements: communication; content creation; critical thinking; lifelong learning.

This study core argument revolves around transdisciplinary integration of emotional intelligence and transformative skills within educational frameworks, prioritizing competencies such as resilience, empathy, well-being, and sustainability [38]. These priorities are directly aligned with the IDG framework, which emphasizes the development of inner capacities to empower students to navigate a VUCA (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity) world effectively [43, 44]. As concerns over mental health and sustainability become more pressing, the imperative for universities to embed these competencies within curricula and campus life is clear, ensuring a holistic approach to student development [34, 35].

Therefore, this study dives into the transformative potential of SMART Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and international management and business schools in shaping a more inclusive and democratized educational landscape for a 5.0 society. These institutions advocate for interconnected, ethically informed, and networked learning practices that not only keep pace with technological changes but also remain grounded in sustainable and inclusive development goals. By adopting such a comprehensive approach, educational systems can better prepare graduates to be future-ready leaders who are equipped to drive positive change in society. It underscores the importance of both inner and outer sustainability within educational ecosystems [36, 41, 42].

The paper explores processes of change in sustainability education at the individual, collective, and system levels, drawing on [40], and underscores the importance of resilience and creativity in climate resilience education, focusing on empowering students to transition from climate anxiety to resilience and regeneration [46]. By integrating these insights with metamodernist frameworks [45] the study advocates for an educational approach that balances technical skills with emotional management, inner development, and sustainability-oriented competencies [44], essential for thriving in the digital metamodern era. The article analyzes the correlation between future skills needs identified by the WEF, learning patterns on Coursera, and the IDGs framework, aiming to uncover gaps and propose strategies for better alignment.

Interoperability for e-skills and AI skills is ensured by the communicative nature [18] of interdisciplinary skills in general. The core cross-sectorial domain that is referential for primary skills (social skills, emotional intellect, collaboration, communication, digital literacy), necessary for educational goals achievement, is estimated to be COMMUNICATION, DIGITAL LITERACY, GEN-AI LITERACY in its turn is defined as the ability to use information and communication technologies to find, evaluate, create, and communicate information, requiring both cognitive and technical skills [5; 10; 28]. Digital literacy and e-skills assessment in the educational context has been subject to academic reevaluation due to the objective conditions of the pandemic global lockdown measures and has been approached through different lens: regional variation in digital literacy level development in education [16]; technological challenges for development of soft skills [21]; challenges and opportunities of e-learning in higher education [1].

The study premise is based on identification of various competency principles, derivative of 21st century skills [4; 7; 9; 11; 24; 31] for education stakeholders and projected digital and AI literacy requirements.

The study identifies and categorizes critical competencies highlighted consistently or emerging across the years in both sets of reports, creating a robust analytical framework for assessing patterns such as skill emergence, consistency, or decline. Subsequently, these identified skills gaps are explicitly aligned with the Inner Development Goals (IDGs) framework, aligning competencies within its five dimensions—*Being, Thinking, Relating, Collaborating, and Acting*. This detailed alignment enables the study to propose specific curricular strategies for integrating Emotional Intelligence (EQ) and inner developmental competencies, through the integration of EQ and IDGs into higher education curricula is proposed through Kotter's 8-Step Change Framework.

The study bridges identified transdisciplinary gaps in student employability in a rapidly evolving complex and digitized professional environment of the multilateral polarization that is coming after the era of globalization.

The analysis reveals alignment in some technical areas between WEF's projected skills and Coursera learners' focus, but significant gaps persist in cognitive and soft skills. Employers highly value skills like *Analytical Thinking, Complex Problem-Solving, and Active Learning*, which are underemphasized in current learning trends. Similarly, crucial soft skills like *Emotional Intelligence, Resilience, and Adaptability* are also underrepresented, despite their growing importance.

The IDGs address these transdisciplinary gaps by focusing on inner development alongside technical skills. The *Thinking* dimension of the IDGs promotes cognitive abilities like analytical thinking and problem-solving, while the *Being* and *Relating* dimensions include emotional intelligence, empathy, and resilience. By incorporating the IDGs into education and professional development, a balanced skill set that aligns with current and future job market demands can be achieved.

Educational institutions and organizations can bridge the skills gap by integrating the IDGs into curricula, teaching methods, and assessments. This involves embedding IDG competencies into course objectives, promoting self-awareness and collaboration, and developing evaluation methods to measure both personal growth and soft skills. Organizations can adopt the IDGs to enhance professional development and corporate social responsibility with cultures that value inner growth and sustainable practices.

A *complex skill* is generally understood as a skill requiring to process lots of information and make lots of decisions

simultaneously [23; 32]. That way, a comprehensive correspondence between 21st century skills framework, Competences 2020 framework [22] and the newly introduced Global Skills 2025 framework [31] has been devised and upgraded.

The transdisciplinary integration between the corresponding skillsets across various frameworks could be referred to the following key domains of human activity [23]:

- COMMUNICATION;
- COGNITIVE ACTIVITY;
- PERSONAL INTERACTION;
- SOCIAL ACTIVITY;
- HEURISTICS;
- AI-INTERACTION.

Interoperability of Core Skills and Digital Skills in Education

The future landscape of work will place a premium on cognitive skills, particularly creative and analytical thinking, as businesses navigate complex challenges. Self-efficacy skills are becoming increasingly vital, with employers seeking workers who are adaptable, resilient, and committed to lifelong learning. While some traditional skills may see a relative decline in importance, the need for technology literacy and ethical competencies is on the rise, driven by technological advancements and societal expectations. Industry-specific trends highlight the necessity for tailored skill development strategies to meet the evolving demands of different sectors.

The World Economic Forum's Future of Jobs Reports 2023-2024 highlight a significant emphasis on socio-emotional skills, referred to as "Attitudes" within the Global Skills Taxonomy. Across various industries, approximately two-thirds of the skills that companies identify as priorities for workforce development fall under the Skills, Knowledge, and Abilities cluster (often termed "hard skills"), while the remaining one-third consists of Attitudes.

Socio-emotional skills are becoming increasingly prioritized, with attitudes reaching parity with technical skills in training programs. **Leadership and social influence** have emerged as key strategic priorities for businesses between 2023 and 2027, surpassing their current ranking as core worker skills and emphasizing their growing role in business success and workforce adaptability.

Trends in skills strategies show a balance between **collaboration and self-efficacy skills**, with many sectors emphasizing working with others, such as **empathy, active listening, and leadership, over self-management**. However, teaching and mentoring skills are receiving minimal attention in most training programs, suggesting a potential gap in nurturing interpersonal guidance roles.

The approach to self-efficacy skills varies, with some sectors focusing on **resilience, flexibility, and agility**, while others prioritize curiosity and lifelong learning, reflecting the need for continuous personal and professional growth. **Motivation and self-awareness** are also emphasized, promoting personal development and growth management.

Ethical thinking shows varied levels of prioritization across sectors, with some focusing more on upskilling employees in these areas. Though **global citizenship** is not widely prioritized, **environmental stewardship** is increasingly recognized as a key component in skill strategies, often with a higher perceived future importance than current demand. This shift reflects the rising need for green skills and the growing trend toward Green Digital economy.

To gain further insights into these evolving trends, we will analyze the top skills reported from 2018 to 2023. A heat map categorizing skills as Consistent, Emerging, Rising, Declining, or Re-emerging will help visualize changes in learner interests and priorities (Table 1):

Skill	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Leadership and Management	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent
Communication	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent
Business Strategy / Strategy and Operations	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent
Entrepreneurship	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent
Digital Marketing				Emerging	Rising	Rising
Sustainability Management						Emerging
Innovation					Emerging	Rising
Diversity and Inclusion						Emerging
Project Management	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent
Finance	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent
Accounting	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Declining
Human Resources	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Declining
Sales	Consistent	Consistent	Consistent	Declining	Declining	Declining

Table 1. Hotmap Analysis of the Top Skills in Global Skills Reports

Subsequently, mapping of core Global Skills across the IDG Framework is feasible across such dimensions (Fig. 1):

The **Being** dimension aligns with WEF's emphasis on personal resilience, emotional intelligence, and active learning. Resilience and Stress Tolerance through Inner Peace and Self-Awareness, enabling individuals to manage stress and adapt to change. An Openness and Learning Mindset promotes Active Learning, encouraging continuous personal growth.

The **Thinking** dimension directly addresses the cognitive skills highlighted by the WEF. Critical Thinking and Complexity Awareness enhance Analytical Thinking and Complex Problem-Solving abilities. Perspective Skills and Sense-Making contribute to Creativity and Innovation by allowing individuals to integrate diverse viewpoints and generate novel solutions.

The **Relating** dimension integrates Emotional Intelligence and enhances Leadership through Empathy, Compassion, and a sense of Connectedness. By cultivating these qualities, individuals are better equipped to understand and influence others positively.

The **Collaborating** dimension emphasizes effective teamwork and social interaction, aligning with WEF's focus on Leadership and Social Influence. Communication Skills and an Inclusive Mindset enhance Emotional Intelligence and the ability to lead diverse teams.

The **Acting** dimension supports proactive engagement and innovation. Creativity and Courage enable individuals to take initiative and drive change, resonating with WEF's emphasis on Creativity and Initiative. Agency and Perseverance facilitate continuous learning and adaptation, essential for technological proficiency.

Figure 1: Global Skills Mapping Across IDGs Framework

Furthermore, the study stipulates that digital interoperability for Arts and Humanities skills is ensured by the communicative nature of transdisciplinary skills. The core cross-sectorial domain that is referential for primary skills (social skills, emotional intellect, collaboration, communication, Digital and AI-literacy), necessary for educational goals achievement, is COMMUNICATION.

Given the nature of increasingly digitalized context of foreign languages education and communicative application (“the Technospheric shift” [30] and the Age of AI [15; 23]), it is

suggested to consider the different types of information source and information destination (human and machine / computer / program, accordingly) in the structure of the groundwork Communication model (Cf. Claude Shannon [25]), when communication is approached as the core factor of interoperability of source and target knowledge and application domains – both for human and machine interactive purposes (Fig. 2):

Figure 2: AI-interoperable Communication Cycle in Education

Therefore, an INTEROPERABLE DIGITAL SKILL for the purpose of this study is defined as a rhizomatic (virally acquired) capability of mutually informed manipulation of digital data, tools, and communication formats, acquired institutionally, intuitively or on the peer-to-peer basis.

Subsequently, the interoperable digital skills for AI-enhanced professional activity are modeled across the skills domains of professional activity (as determined by the different competence frameworks) and core domains of professional literacy (Fig. 3):

Figure 3: Interoperability of Core Skills and Digital/AI-Literacy Frameworks

The study aims to identify, among other parameters, challenges for actual and underdeveloped cross-sectorial and transdisciplinary skills (hard, technical and soft), that participants of the educational process encountered through the pandemic and warfare emergency digital education measures.

IDG-interoperable Digital and AI-proof Skills for Education

A sizable sample of 372 respondents total had been polled across the wartime timeframe (2022-2025).

Diagnostics of specialists in Arts and Sciences according to European e-Competence Framework and estimation of digital skills for professional application - allowed to evaluate of the professional e-competence dimensions among the following: A. PLAN, B. BUILD, C. RUN, D. ENABLE and E. MANAGE professional processes with the help of digital and AI-powered tools and services.

Within the given dimensions the following top scoring professional goals were estimated: 1) Planning of professional processes (with the help of AI) (A) – 61% of respondents; 2) Monitoring of professional activity (with the help of AI) (C) – 50% of respondents; 3) Provision (facilitation) of professional activity (with the help of AI) (D) – 47% of respondents. According to the prioritized professional goals, the followings dominant professional e-competence dimensions are identified: 1) to PLAN; 2) to RUN; 3) to ENABLE professional processes with the help of AI (for communication and education).

The priority types of dominant digital skills for professional application according to the European e-competence framework are estimated as 1) ICT and Gen AI user skills – 75% of respondents; 2) ICT and Gen AI practitioner skills – 74% of respondents.

According to the Likert Scale assessment ICT and Gen AI user skills get a top ranking of 4 (46% of respondents) and ICT and Gen AI practitioner skills get a top ranking of 5 (37% of respondents).

The following specific digital skills for professionals correspond to the prioritized types: 1) ICT and Gen AI PRACTITIONER SKILLS: Skills for language and communication research; Skills for strategic planning of communication; Skills for

communicative management; Skills for consulting; 2) ICT and Gen AI USER SKILLS: Skills for the effective application of ICT systems and devices; Skills to apply ICT systems and GPT models as tools in support of one’s workflow; User skills to use of common software tools and of specialized AI tools supporting business functions within professional area of communicative use.

Diagnostics of digital skills for pre-service and in-service teachers according to UNESCO AI Competence Frameworks (teachers/students) – allowed to identify 1) professional activity goals for digital and AI skills application and 2) student-oriented goals of pre-service teachers for digital and AI skills application. The priority (scoring 5-4 on the evaluation scale) professional activity goals for digital and AI skills application are estimated by the stakeholders as: 1) to improve one’s own teaching skills with digital tools and AI tools (65% of respondents). 2) to develop learning materials using digital and AI-powered tools (60% of respondents); 3) to understand the role of digital technologies in language generation and AI-mediated communication (59% of respondents); 4) to develop curricula using digital and AI-powered tools (53% of respondents).

The priority (scoring 5-4 on the evaluation scale) student oriented goals for digital and AI skills application are estimated as: 1) to help learn independently via digital and AI tools (66% of respondents); 2) to help to become effective participants in civil society through digital and AI tools (61% of respondents); 3) to teach to solve problems with digital and AI tools (59% of respondents); 4) to teach to think critically using digital and AI tools (54% of respondents); 5) to teach to implement different types of communicative activities (oral, written, listening, dialogue, monologue) – 54% respondents; 6) to teach to work in a team / organize collaboration with AI-powered tools (53% of respondents);

It bears pointing out that the dominant students-oriented goals for digital and AI skills application correspond to the generic soft skills, identified across various frameworks: 1) Learning and innovation; 2) human resources management, social intellect; 3) adaptability and resilience; 4) problem solving and critical thinking; 5) collaboration and communication (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: IDGs-interoperable Core skills in Digital Education Frameworks

Therefore, AI-Proof and AI-Ready Skills are central to navigating an AI-driven world. *AI-Proof Skills*, like empathy, compassion, complex problem-solving, and ethical judgment, are inherently human and challenging for AI to replicate. These skills emphasize social dynamics and moral reasoning. *AI-Ready Skills* enable effective collaboration with AI technologies, requiring a learning mindset, sense-making, creativity, and innovation to harness AI's strategic potential.

The IDG framework enhances human-AI collaboration by equipping individuals with creativity, ethical awareness, and agency to use AI innovatively while navigating its moral implications. Aligning with WEF's and the Global Skills Index focus on cognitive, emotional, and social skills, the IDGs cultivate both AI-proof and AI-ready competencies. This approach bridges traditional skills gaps by integrating inner development alongside technical proficiency, preparing individuals for success in an AI-integrated workforce.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The warfare emergency e-learning measures and underlying shift in the digital economy of Europe towards the rise of AI informed the comprehensive modelling of interoperability between various competency principles, derivative of the soft marketable skills and projected digital literacy requirements across core digital literacy frameworks.

Digital domain, digital communication and digital, AI-empowered, literacy are assessed as interoperable parameters across different e-competence frameworks, that inform underlying interdisciplinarity of Arts and Sciences education in the timespan of the wartime emergency e-learning measures.

Evaluation of digital and AI-interoperable skills for professional application allowed to determine the priority dimensions of professional e-competence as *to plan, to run and to enable* professional processes with the help of AI-powered tools and services. The types of dominant digital skills for professional application of are identified as ICT and AI *user skills* and ICT and AI *practitioner skills*. The demands of digital and knowledge economy job market are not met by the Arts and Sciences curriculum design, as the *e-business* skills are evaluated scoring lowest in priority by stakeholders.

The dominant AI-interoperable skills acquired are: communication, emotional intellect, creativity, problem solving and innovation. Digital and AI literacy features as a prominent interoperable skill, facilitating the application of other types of soft skills of the communicative nature.

To effectively integrate inner development and emotional intelligence (EQ) within SMAR universities for AI-powered economy, both curricula and educators' skillsets must undergo strategic change.

For **Individuals**, embracing the Inner Development Goals (IDGs) framework through university programs can strengthen inner capacities in tandem with technical skills. Universities should embed EQ, adaptability, and self-awareness into both curricular and extracurricular activities. This integration could involve modules on self-reflection, mindfulness, and collaborative learning experiences that promote resilience and adaptability. Such an approach not only enhances students' ability to thrive in a technology-driven workforce but also equips them with critical soft skills for ethical decision-making, teamwork, and personal growth. Encouraging self-directed learning and peer mentoring can further deepen these capacities. For **Organizations**, particularly within academic institutions, the IDG framework should be adopted as a core component of faculty development. Training programs focused on cultivating

empathy, creativity, and critical thinking among teachers are crucial. Educators must shift from traditional teaching models to becoming facilitators of learning, guiding students in developing both their technical and inner capacities. Workshops on developing emotional intelligence, practicing inclusive teaching methods, and a growth mindset can support educators in nurturing well-rounded, innovative, and ethically responsible graduates. Promoting a culture of continuous professional development within universities ensures that educators stay agile and effective as change agents.

For **Policymakers and Curriculum Designers**, SMART universities must align their curricula with IDG principles by prioritizing holistic, learner-centered development. This requires a rethinking of current academic structures to incorporate EQ and inner development as foundational competencies, not just supplementary skills. Strategies might include project-based learning with a focus on real-world challenges that require ethical considerations, emotional self-regulation, and collaboration. Moreover, curriculum revisions should emphasize interdisciplinary learning, merging technical knowledge with socio-emotional competencies. A mindset of inner development among educators and students alike requires the curriculum of a transformative experience that prepares individuals to navigate the complexities of the digital era and emerging global challenges effectively.

The perspective of the study is in scaling the inquiry to estimate the dimensions of digital and AI literacy formation for for different types of e-learning tools, as well as to diagnose interdisciplinary, AI-powered digitization trends across countries of Europe.

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